

phenols, it has been found that the condensations take place more readily and with greater yield when the acid is replaced by an ester.

The alkaline solutions of all the above compounds are deep red showing a beautiful green fluorescence on dilution. They dye yellow to orange shades while their bromo-compounds dye red shades. The fluorescence is entirely subdued in the case of *o*-nitro-resorcinol benzoin due to the effect of the nitro-group. On the other hand the nitro-group increases the reactivity of the ester as the condensation takes place at a lower temperature.

The fluorescence in the case of *o*- and *p*-aminobenzoins changes to a bluish shade on standing.

Resorcinol naphthalein exhibits similar fluorescence to resorcinol benzoin but dyes deeper shades.

When the benzene ring is replaced by aliphatic residues having high molecular weights as in resorcinol olein and resorcinol stearein, the shade of the dye becomes deeper although the affinity to the fibre becomes less.

There is a remarkable difference in the solubility between the two compounds, olein and stearein, the former being insoluble in benzene ; and this fact has been utilised in separating the condensation products of the glycerides of the saturated fatty acids in natural oils with resorcinol, from those derived from unsaturated fatty acids.

The natural oils (glycerides) being analogous to esters have been similarly condensed with resorcinol. Coconut oil, olive oil and castor oil have been made to yield dyes in this way producing yellow to brown shades on wool and silk, bright red shades being produced by the bromo-compounds. The easy methods of preparation, the cheapness of the starting materials and the high yields (80%) increase the possibility of these dyestuffs acquiring commercial importance.

Benzoic ester and its *o*-hydroxy-derivative have also been condensed with dimethylaniline, to give malachite green and *o*-hydroxy-malachite green. The nature of the condensing agent is very important. After the failure with zinc chloride (alone and in presence of gaseous hydrochloric acid) it has been found that a mixture of phosphorous oxychloride and zinc chloride brings about the desired reaction with satisfactory yield. The dye base is in each case formed directly, subsequent oxidation being not necessary.

This is the chief advantage of this new method of preparing the malachite green dyes. The reaction may be represented thus:—

Malachite green was previously obtained by condensing dimethylaniline with benzoic acid (D R.-P. 101426) but the yield, by using benzoic ester instead, is much more satisfactory.

Rhodamines have been obtained by the condensation of diethyl-*m*-aminophenol with benzoic, anthranilic and stearic esters in presence of zinc chloride.

The anthranilorhodamine is not a deeper dye than benzorhodamine while the rhodamine derived from stearine is a much feebler dye than benzorhodamine and resembles Pyronine G.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Resorcinol benzoin.—Resorcinol (8 g.) and ethyl benzoate (7.5 c.c.) are heated with zinc chloride (10 g.) at 180° for 5 hours, dry hydrochloric acid gas being passed into the mixture. The product is

washed with hot water acidified with hydrochloric acid and then dissolved in caustic soda. After filtering, the solution is diluted to a large bulk in a basin, cooled in ice and neutralised with dilute acetic acid. After filtration, the product is dried and extracted with benzene, ether and chloroform and is finally crystallised as a yellow microcrystalline powder from dilute alcohol. It is then recrystallised from nitrobenzene. The substance is identical with resorcinolbenzein (Sen and Sinha, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, **45**, 2985) (yield 80%) (Found: C, 73·8; H, 4·1. $C_{19}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 79·16; H, 4·16 per cent.).

Monopotassium Salt.—Prepared as in the above paper (*loc. cit.*). Deep red fluorescent solid. (Found: K, 11·55. $C_{19}H_{11}O_3K$ requires K, 11·99 per cent.).

The bromo-derivative decomposes at 200°. (Found: Br, 52·5. $C_{19}H_8O_3Br_4$ requires Br, 52·98 per cent.).

Other compounds of the benzein series together with their derivatives are listed in the table on Benzeins.

2:4 Dihydroxybenzophenone.—Ethyl benzoate (1 mol.) and resorcinol (1 mol.) are heated with zinc chloride to 140° for 5 hours. The product is crystallised from hot water; yellow needles, m. p. 144° (yield, 10%); identical in every respect with 2:4-dihydroxybenzophenone. (*Annalen*, 1881, **210**, 256; *Ber.*, 1894, **27**, 1287; 1901, **34**, 2337) (Found: C, 72·5; H, 4·5. $C_{13}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 72·9; H, 4·6 per cent.).

2:3:4-Trihydroxybenzophenone.—Ethyl benzoate (1 mol.) and pyrogallol (1 mol.) are heated with zinc chloride to 140° for 4 hrs. The product was purified by repeated crystallisations from hot water. Yellow needles, m. p. 140°; soluble in ether, alcohol and benzene (yield, 15%) (*Ber.*, 1810, **23**, 42; *Annalen*, 1892, **269**, 297). (Found: C, 67·0, 67·1; H, 4·8, 4·7. $C_{13}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 67·8; H, 4·3 per cent.).

Name.	Formula.	Preparation.	Appearance and m.p.		Analysis:		Properties.
			Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	
Resorcinol- <i>o</i> -nitrobenzein.	$C_{10}H_{11}O_4N$.	<i>o</i> -Nitrobenzoic ester + resorcinol + $ZnCl_2$ at 140° for 4 hrs. Yield, 80%.	Yellow micro-crystalline. Does not melt up to 290° .	6.49 (N)	6.5%		Soluble in alcohol and acetone, very sparingly in chloroform, insoluble in ether. Brownish-yellow shades on wool and silk. Alkaline solution non-fluorescent.
Resorcinol- <i>o</i> -amino-benzein.	$C_{10}H_{11}O_3$.	Anthranilic ester + resorcinol + $ZnCl_2$ at 180° for 6 hrs.	Softens near 175° .	4.6 (N)	4.6%		Identical with the same compound by Sen and Guha-Sarar. (<i>J. Indian Chem. Soc.</i> , 1924, 1, 164).
Resorcinol- <i>p</i> -amino-benzein.	$C_{10}H_{11}O_3N$.	<i>p</i> -Aminobenzoic ester + resorcinol. Yield, 80%.	Decomposes at 290° .	4.6 (N)	4.6%		Red-green fluorescence in alkaline soln. changing to blue on standing. Soluble in alcohol, acetone, insoluble in ether, chloroform and benzene. Orange shades on wool and silk, deeper than the <i>o</i> -amino-compound.
Dibromo-derivative.	$C_{10}H_{11}O_3NBr_2$.	Bromination of the above compound.	Plates from alcohol.	34.7 (Br)	34.5%		Dyes wool and silk red shades.
Resorcinol naphthalin.	$C_{23}H_{17}O_3$.	Naphthoic ester + resorcinol. Yield, 80%.	Similar to resorcinol benzein. Does not melt up to 290° .	81.6 (C) 4.6 (H)	81.7% 4.6%		Similar to resorcinol benzein. Dyes deeper orange shades. Alkaline soln. shows red-green fluorescence.
Tetrabromo-derivative.	$C_{23}H_{17}O_3Br_4$.	Bromination of above.	Plates from alcohol. Decomposes at 260° .	48.9 (Br)	48.2%		Red shades on wool and silk
Resorcinol stearin.	$C_{31}H_{41}O_4$.	Stearic ester + resorcinol. Yield, 70%.	Softens at 160° .	80 (C)	79.6%		Soluble in benzene (Sen and Guha-Sarar. (<i>loc. cit.</i>).
Resorcinol olein.	$C_{30}H_{40}O_3$.	Oleic ester + resorcinol. Yield, 80%.	Softens at 140° .	80.30 (C) 8.9 (H)	80.0% 9.2%		Soluble in alcohol (red-green). Ethyl acetate (yellow) no fluorescence. Sparingly soluble in ether, insoluble in benzene, and petroleum ether. Orange shades on wool and silk.
Hexabromo-derivative.	$C_{30}H_{40}O_3Br_6$.	Bromination of above.		51.9 (Br)	51.7%		Dyes wool and silk red shades.

Condensation of Natural Oils with Resorcinol.

Name of oil.	Preparation.	Appearance.	Analysis.	Properties.
Olive oil.	Olive oil (4 g.) + resorcinol (6 g.) + $ZnCl_2$ (4 g.) at 180° (4 hrs.). Separated into two fractions by benzene, in which the condensation products of the glycerides of the saturated fatty acids with resorcinol are soluble. Total yield, 80%. Purified from alcohol.	Brown amorphous powders (both fractions).	<i>Benzene fraction:</i> C, 70.3; H, 8.3% <i>Resorcinol stearin:</i> requires C, 80; H, 9.3%. <i>Main fraction:</i> C, 75.7; H, 9.6%.	<i>Benzene fraction:</i> Similar to resorcinol stearin. Other fraction, soluble in alcohol (red-green), sparingly soluble in ether and insoluble in benzene. Dyes wool brownish shades.
Bromo-derivative.	Bromination of an alcoholic solution of the portion insoluble in benzene.	Red powder.	...	Dyes wool and silk red shades.
Castor oil.	Castor oil (6 g.) resorcinol (4 g.) at 180° with $ZnCl_2$. Purification as above.	Brownish powder.	...	Alcoholic and alkaline solns. fluorescent. Dyes wool and silk orange shades.
Bromo-compound.	Bromination of the above compound.	Red powder.	...	Dyes wool and silk red shades.
Cocconut oil.	Oil (5 g.) + resorcinol (4 g.)	Brown amorphous powder.	...	Similar to the other compounds, but fluorescence deeper. Dyes wool and silk orange shades, brighter than any of the above products.
Bromo-compound.	Bromination of the above compound.	Red powder.	...	Dyes wool and silk red shades.

Triphenylmethane Dyes.

Name.	Formula.	Preparation.	Appearance and m.p.	Analysis. Calc.	Properties.
Malachite green.	$C_{25}H_{18}ON_3$.	Dimethylamine (2 mols.) + ethyl benzoate (1 mol.) heated with an upright air condenser with $ZnCl_2$ and $POCl_3$ (6 hrs). Made alkaline with $NaOH$, distilled in steam till free from dimethylaniline, dissolved in boiling HCl and pptd. with $NaOH$. Purified from chloroform. Yield, 75%.	Semi-solid mass.	8.16(N) 8.0%.	Has all the properties of malachite green.
<i>o</i> -Hydroxy-malachite green.	$C_{23}H_{16}N_2O_3$.	Ethyl salicylate and dimethylaniline. Purification as above.	Bluish-green semi-solid mass.	7.74(N) 7.6%	Dyes wool and silk and tanned cotton bluish-green shades.
<i>Rhodamines.</i>					
Benzorhodamine.	$C_{31}H_{23}O_3N_3$.	Diethyl- <i>m</i> -aminophenol (3 mols.) and ethyl benzoate (1 mol.) + $ZnCl_2$ at 160° for 6 hrs. washed with hot water, dissolved in dil. HCl and pptd. with Na_2CO_3 . Crystallised from absolute alcohol. Yield, 65%.	Violet powder, softens at 210° .	7.5 (N) 7.6%.	Alcoholic soln. exhibits violet fluorescence. Dyes wool, silk and tanned cotton bluish-red.
Anthranilorhodamine.	$C_{31}H_{23}O_4N_3$.	Ethyl anthranilate and diethyl- <i>m</i> -aminophenol. Yield, 70%.	Pink powder, softens at 225° .	9.74 (N) 9.6%.	Identical with same compound by Sen and Guha-Sircar, (<i>loc. cit.</i>).
Stearicrhodamine.	$C_{33}H_{41}N_3O_2$.	From ethyl stearate. Yield, 80%.	Red powder.	5.36 (N) 5.9%	Soluble in ether, alcohol (violet fluorescence) and chloroform. Dyes wool, silk and tanned cotton pink shades.

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